

Sharkrf

```
processing.run("otb:TrainImagesClassifier",
{'io.il':['E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/SR/LC08_L1TP_004056_20170302_20200905_02_T1_PSH.tif'],'io.vd':
['E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/Mosaico2017.shp'],'io.valid':None,'io.imstat':'E:\\Trabajo\\Tesis\\2017\\
SR\\CLASII\\Estadisticas_LC08_L1TP_004056_20170302_20200905_02_T1_PSH.xml','io.out':'E:/Tr
abajo/Tesis/2017/SR/CLASII/MODELOS/sharkrf.txt','io.confmatout':'E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/SR/CLA
SII/MODELOS/sharkrf.csv','cleanup':True,'sample.mt':1000,'sample.mv':1000,'sample.bm':1,'sampl
e.vtr':0.5,'sample.vfn':'Classvalue','elev.dem':'','elev.geoid':'','elev.default':0,'classifier':'sharkrf','cla
ssifier.sharkrf.nbtrees':100,'classifier.sharkrf.nodesize':25,'classifier.sharkrf.mtry':0,'classifier.shark
rf.oobr':0.66,'rand':0})
```

KNN

```
processing.run("otb:TrainImagesClassifier",
{'io.il':['E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/SR/LC08_L1TP_004056_20170302_20200905_02_T1_PSH.tif'],'io.vd':
['E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/Mosaico2017.shp'],'io.valid':None,'io.imstat':'E:\\Trabajo\\Tesis\\2017\\
SR\\CLASII\\Estadisticas_LC08_L1TP_004056_20170302_20200905_02_T1_PSH.xml','io.out':'E:/Tr
abajo/Tesis/2017/SR/CLASII/MODELOS/knn.txt','io.confmatout':'E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/SR/CLASII/
MODELOS/knnrkf.csv','cleanup':True,'sample.mt':1000,'sample.mv':1000,'sample.bm':1,'sample.v
tr':0.5,'sample.vfn':'Classvalue','elev.dem':'','elev.geoid':'','elev.default':0,'classifier':'knn','classifier
.knn.k':32,'rand':0})
```

RandomForest

```
processing.run("otb:TrainImagesClassifier",
{'io.il':['E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/SR/LC08_L1TP_004056_20170302_20200905_02_T1_PSH.tif'],'io.vd':
['E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/Mosaico2017.shp'],'io.valid':None,'io.imstat':'E:\\Trabajo\\Tesis\\2017\\
SR\\CLASII\\Estadisticas_LC08_L1TP_004056_20170302_20200905_02_T1_PSH.xml','io.out':'E:/Tr
abajo/Tesis/2017/SR/CLASII/MODELOS/rf.txt','io.confmatout':'E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/SR/CLASII/M
ODELOS/rf.csv','cleanup':True,'sample.mt':1000,'sample.mv':1000,'sample.bm':1,'sample.vtr':0.5,'s
ample.vfn':'Classvalue','elev.dem':'','elev.geoid':'','elev.default':0,'classifier':'rf','classifier.rf.max':5,'
classifier.rf.min':10,'classifier.rf.ra':0,'classifier.rf.cat':10,'classifier.rf.var':0,'classifier.rf.nbtrees':10
0,'classifier.rf.acc':0.01,'rand':0})
```

BAYES

```
processing.run("otb:TrainImagesClassifier",
{'io.il':['E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/SR/LC08_L1TP_004056_20170302_20200905_02_T1_PSH.tif'],'io.vd':
['E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/Mosaico2017.shp'],'io.valid':None,'io.imstat':'E:\\Trabajo\\Tesis\\2017\\
SR\\CLASII\\Estadisticas_LC08_L1TP_004056_20170302_20200905_02_T1_PSH.xml','io.out':'E:/Tr
abajo/Tesis/2017/SR/CLASII/MODELOS/bayes.txt','io.confmatout':'E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/SR/CLAS
II/MODELOS/bayes.csv','cleanup':True,'sample.mt':1000,'sample.mv':1000,'sample.bm':1,'sample.
```

```
vtr':0.5,'sample.vfn':'Classvalue','elev.dem':'','elev.geoid':'','elev.default':0,'classifier':'bayes','rand':0})
```

ann

```
processing.run("otb:TrainImagesClassifier",  
{'io.il':['E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/SR/LC08_L1TP_004056_20170302_20200905_02_T1_PSH.tif'],'io.vd':  
:['E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/Mosaico2017.shp'],'io.valid':None,'io.imstat':'E:\\Trabajo\\Tesis\\2017\\  
SR\\CLASII\\Estadisticas_LC08_L1TP_004056_20170302_20200905_02_T1_PSH.xml'],'io.out':'E:/Tr  
abajo/Tesis/2017/SR/CLASII/MODELOS/ann.txt'],'io.confmatout':'E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/SR/CLASII/  
MODELOS/ann.csv'],'cleanup':True,'sample.mt':1000,'sample.mv':1000,'sample.bm':1,'sample.vtr':  
0.5,'sample.vfn':'Classvalue','elev.dem':'','elev.geoid':'','elev.default':0,'classifier':'ann',  
classifier.ann.n.t':'reg',classifier.ann.sizes':'200',classifier.ann.f':'sig',classifier.ann.a':1,  
classifier.ann.b':1,'classifier.ann.bpdw':0.1,'classifier.ann.bpms':0.1,'classifier.ann.rdw':0.1,  
classifier.ann.rdwm':0,'classifier.ann.term':'all',classifier.ann.eps':0.01,'classifier.ann.iter':1000,'rand':0})
```

bost

```
processing.run("otb:TrainImagesClassifier",  
{'io.il':['E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/SR/LC08_L1TP_004056_20170302_20200905_02_T1_PSH.tif'],'io.vd':  
:['E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/Mosaico2017.shp'],'io.valid':None,'io.imstat':'E:\\Trabajo\\Tesis\\2017\\  
SR\\CLASII\\Estadisticas_LC08_L1TP_004056_20170302_20200905_02_T1_PSH.xml'],'io.out':'E:/Tr  
abajo/Tesis/2017/SR/CLASII/MODELOS/boost.txt'],'io.confmatout':'E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/SR/CLASI  
I/MODELOS/boost.csv'],'cleanup':True,'sample.mt':1000,'sample.mv':1000,'sample.bm':1,'sample.v  
tr':0.5,'sample.vfn':'Classvalue','elev.dem':'','elev.geoid':'','elev.default':0,'classifier':'boost',  
classifier.boost.t':'real',classifier.boost.w':100,'classifier.boost.r':0.95,'classifier.boost.m':1,'rand':0})
```

SVM sigmoid

```
processing.run("otb:TrainImagesClassifier",  
{'io.il':['E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/SR/LC08_L1TP_004056_20170302_20200905_02_T1_PSH.tif'],'io.vd':  
:['E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/Mosaico2017.shp'],'io.valid':None,'io.imstat':'E:\\Trabajo\\Tesis\\2017\\  
SR\\CLASII\\Estadisticas_LC08_L1TP_004056_20170302_20200905_02_T1_PSH.xml'],'io.out':'E:/Tr  
abajo/Tesis/2017/SR/CLASII/MODELOS/SVM_sigmoid.txt'],'io.confmatout':'E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/  
SR/CLASII/MODELOS/SVM_sigmoid.csv'],'cleanup':True,'sample.mt':1000,'sample.mv':1000,'sampl  
e.bm':1,'sample.vtr':0.5,'sample.vfn':'Classvalue','elev.dem':'','elev.geoid':'','elev.default':0,'classifi  
er':'libsvm',classifier.libsvm.k':'sigmoid',classifier.libsvm.m':'csvc',classifier.libsvm.c':1,'classifier.li  
bsvm.gamma':1,'classifier.libsvm.coef0':0,'classifier.libsvm.degree':3,'classifier.libsvm.nu':0.5,'class  
ifier.libsvm.opt':True,'classifier.libsvm.prob':True,'rand':0})
```

SVM poly

```
processing.run("otb:TrainImagesClassifier",  
{'io.il':['E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/SR/LC08_L1TP_004056_20170302_20200905_02_T1_PSH.tif'],'io.vd':  
:['E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/Mosaico2017.shp'],'io.valid':None,'io.imstat':'E:\\Trabajo\\Tesis\\2017\\
```

```
SR\\CLASII\\Estadisticas_LC08_L1TP_004056_20170302_20200905_02_T1_PSH.xml', 'io.out': 'E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/SR/CLASII/MODELOS/SVM_poly.txt', 'io.confmatout': 'E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/SR/CLASII/MODELOS/SVM_poly.csv', 'cleanup': True, 'sample.mt': 1000, 'sample.mv': 1000, 'sample.bm': 1, 'sample.vtr': 0.5, 'sample.vfn': 'Classvalue', 'elev.dem': '', 'elev.geoid': '', 'elev.default': 0, 'classifier': 'libsvm', 'classifier.libsvm.k': 'poly', 'classifier.libsvm.m': 'csvc', 'classifier.libsvm.c': 1, 'classifier.libsvm.gamma': 1, 'classifier.libsvm.coef0': 0, 'classifier.libsvm.degree': 3, 'classifier.libsvm.nu': 0.5, 'classifier.libsvm.opt': True, 'classifier.libsvm.prob': True, 'rand': 0}}
```

SVM RBF

```
processing.run("otb:TrainImagesClassifier",  
{'io.il': ['E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/SR/LC08_L1TP_004056_20170302_20200905_02_T1_PSH.tif'], 'io.vd': ['E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/Mosaico2017.shp'], 'io.valid': None, 'io.imstat': 'E:\\Trabajo\\Tesis\\2017\\SR\\CLASII\\Estadisticas_LC08_L1TP_004056_20170302_20200905_02_T1_PSH.xml', 'io.out': 'E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/SR/CLASII/MODELOS/SVM_rbf.txt', 'io.confmatout': 'E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/SR/CLASII/MODELOS/SVM_rbf.csv', 'cleanup': True, 'sample.mt': 1000, 'sample.mv': 1000, 'sample.bm': 1, 'sample.vtr': 0.5, 'sample.vfn': 'Classvalue', 'elev.dem': '', 'elev.geoid': '', 'elev.default': 0, 'classifier': 'libsvm', 'classifier.libsvm.k': 'rbf', 'classifier.libsvm.m': 'csvc', 'classifier.libsvm.c': 1, 'classifier.libsvm.gamma': 1, 'classifier.libsvm.coef0': 0, 'classifier.libsvm.degree': 3, 'classifier.libsvm.nu': 0.5, 'classifier.libsvm.opt': True, 'classifier.libsvm.prob': True, 'rand': 0}}
```

SVM linear

```
processing.run("otb:TrainImagesClassifier",  
{'io.il': ['E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/SR/LC08_L1TP_004056_20170302_20200905_02_T1_PSH.tif'], 'io.vd': ['E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/Mosaico2017.shp'], 'io.valid': None, 'io.imstat': 'E:\\Trabajo\\Tesis\\2017\\SR\\CLASII\\Estadisticas_LC08_L1TP_004056_20170302_20200905_02_T1_PSH.xml', 'io.out': 'E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/SR/CLASII/MODELOS/SVM_linear.txt', 'io.confmatout': 'E:/Trabajo/Tesis/2017/SR/CLASII/MODELOS/SVM_linear.csv', 'cleanup': True, 'sample.mt': 1000, 'sample.mv': 1000, 'sample.bm': 1, 'sample.vtr': 0.5, 'sample.vfn': 'Classvalue', 'elev.dem': '', 'elev.geoid': '', 'elev.default': 0, 'classifier': 'libsvm', 'classifier.libsvm.k': 'linear', 'classifier.libsvm.m': 'csvc', 'classifier.libsvm.c': 1, 'classifier.libsvm.gamma': 1, 'classifier.libsvm.coef0': 0, 'classifier.libsvm.degree': 3, 'classifier.libsvm.nu': 0.5, 'classifier.libsvm.opt': True, 'classifier.libsvm.prob': True, 'rand': 0}}
```

```
image=r"D:\Sentinel\Clasificaciones\S2A_MSIL2A_20230501T110621_N0509_R137_T30STF_20230501T154056\S2A_MSIL2A_20230501T110621_N0509_R137_T30STF_20230501T154056_tac.tif"
```

```
app = otb.Registry.CreateApplication("ComputeImagesStatistics")
app.SetParameterStringList("il", [image])
app.SetParameterFloat("bv", 0)
app.SetParameterString("out.xml", 'D:/Sentinel/otro
ejemplo/estadistifastac.xml')
app.ExecuteAndWriteOutput()
```

```
## Train
```

```
app1 = otb.Registry.CreateApplication("TrainImagesClassifier")
app1.SetParameterStringList("io.il", [image])
app1.SetParameterStringList("io.vd",
['D:/Sentinel/Clasificaciones/S2A_MSIL2A_20230501T110621_N0509_R137_T30STF_20230501T154056/Finañ/Nuevas muestras/ConEsta/muestraspoligonos.shp'])
app1.SetParameterString("io.imstat", 'D:/Sentinel/otro
ejemplo/estadistifastac.xml')
app1.SetParameterInt("sample.mv", 100)
app1.SetParameterInt("sample.bm", 1)
app1.SetParameterInt("sample.mt", 100)
app1.SetParameterFloat("sample.vtr", 0.5)
app1.SetParameterString("sample.vfn", "class_id")
app1.SetParameterString("classifier", "libsvm")
app1.SetParameterString("classifier.libsvm.k", "linear")
app1.SetParameterString("classifier.libsvm.m", "csvc")
app1.SetParameterFloat("classifier.libsvm.c", 1)
app1.SetParameterString("classifier.libsvm.opt", "True")
app1.SetParameterString("classifier.libsvm.prob", "True")
app1.SetParameterFloat("classifier.libsvm.gamma", 1)
app1.SetParameterFloat("classifier.libsvm.coef0", 0)
app1.SetParameterFloat("elev.default", 0)
app1.SetParameterString("cleanup", "True")
app1.SetParameterString("io.out", "D:/Sentinel/otro
ejemplo/SVM_linealtac.txt")
app1.SetParameterString("io.confmatout", "D:/Sentinel/otro
ejemplo/SVM_linealtac.csv")
app1.ExecuteAndWriteOutput()
```

```
app2 = otb.Registry.CreateApplication("ImageClassifier")
```

```
app2.SetParameterString("in", image)
app2.SetParameterString("mask", image)
```

```
app2.SetParameterString("imstat", "D:/Sentinel/otro  
ejemplo/estadistifastac.xml")  
app2.SetParameterString("model", "D:/Sentinel/otro  
ejemplo/SVM_linealtac.txt")  
app2.SetParameterInt("nodatalabel", 0)  
app2.SetParameterString("out", "D:/Sentinel/otro  
ejemplo/SVM_linealtac.tif")  
app2.SetParameterString("confmap", "D:/Sentinel/otro  
ejemplo/ConfidenceMAp2tac.tif")  
app2.SetParameterInt("nbclasses", 20)  
app2.ExecuteAndWriteOutput()
```